

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Oral Health Disorders: An Integrative Review of Dental Caries, Gingivitis, and Periodontitis

Nidhika Rana*, Nikhil Koundal, Sneha, Avinash, Muskan, Nitika

Himachal Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research (HIPER), Bela, Nadaun, Himachal Pradesh, India 177033

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 21 May 2026

Keywords:

Dental caries, Streptococcus mutans, dental biofilm, gingivitis, periodontitis, remineralization

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20328050

ABSTRACT

Dental caries remains one of the most prevalent yet preventable oral diseases worldwide, significantly affecting individuals across all age groups. Despite advancements in oral healthcare, the global burden of dental diseases persists, as highlighted by international health organizations. Dental caries is a multifactorial infectious condition involving the interaction of a susceptible host, cariogenic microorganisms, fermentable substrates, and time. The metabolic activity of bacteria such as *Streptococcus mutans* leads to acid production, resulting in demineralization of tooth structures. Alongside caries, periodontal diseases and gingivitis contribute substantially to oral morbidity, often progressing silently until advanced stages. This paper reviews the historical background, etiology, and pathophysiology of major dental diseases, including dental caries, gingivitis, and periodontitis. It also highlights the role of microbial biofilms, host immune responses, and environmental factors in disease progression. The transition from gingivitis to periodontitis involves complex inflammatory mechanisms, cytokine release, and tissue destruction, including alveolar bone loss. Additionally, the paper discusses the structural changes occurring in enamel, dentin, and cementum during tooth decay. Preventive strategies such as improved oral hygiene, dietary modifications, and potential immunological approaches, including vaccine development, are emphasized. Furthermore, commonly used pharmacological treatments, including antibiotics, antiseptics, anti-inflammatory agents, and remineralizing agents, are reviewed with respect to their mechanisms of action.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most prevalent avoidable conditions that is known to be the main cause of oral

discomfort and tooth loss is dental caries. It is a serious oral health condition that prevents people of all ages from achieving and maintaining good oral health [1]. Despite significant advancements

*Corresponding Author: Nidhika Rana

Address: Himachal Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research (HIPER), Bela, Nadaun, Himachal Pradesh, India

Email ✉: nidhikarana465@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

in the oral health of the populace in a number of nations, the WHO noted that the worldwide issue of oral illness still exists. According to WHO, a number of oral diseases are linked to chronic illnesses, and poor oral health may have a significant impact on overall health and quality of life.

Four elements are needed for caries to develop: a) a susceptible host; b) cariogenic flora; c) a suitable substrate; and d) a sufficient amount of time. Increasing the host's resistance, reducing the quantity of microorganisms in touch with the tooth, altering the substrate by choosing non-cariogenic meals, and cutting down on the amount of time the substrate is in the mouth are some of the methods used to prevent caries. Vaccines are created and directed against the antigenic components of the primary causative agent, *S. mutans*, by comprehending the immunology of dental caries. Therefore, dental cavities will be avoided [3].

Dentistry began around 5000 B.C., when dental caries was thought to be caused by "tooth worms." The Latin word "caries," which means decay, is where the term "dental caries" first appeared in literature about 1634. At first, the phrase was used to refer to tooth holes. According to reports, one of the most prevalent and ancient diseases in humans is dental caries. Dental caries is a common chronic infectious illness caused by cariogenic bacteria that cling to teeth and break down sugars to form acid, which eventually demineralizes tooth structure.

A large part of any dentist's daily work involves treating dental caries lesions. Healthy teeth and oral health care are crucial for individuals from all walks of life. Over the course of a person's life, success and productivity are impacted by dental caries' impacts on growth and physical, emotional, and cognitive development [4,5] Dental caries was

shown to be highly prevalent across all age groups in India, according to numerous epidemiological studies conducted in various regions of the country [6].

When cariogenic bacteria and dietary sources of sucrose or refined sugar colonise a susceptible tooth surface, tooth decay results. Bacteria that ferment carbohydrates produce lactic acid, which dissolves the tooth's hydroxyapatite crystal structure and causes caries [7,8]. People's daily lives are greatly impacted by discomfort, difficulties eating, chewing, smiling, and communicating as a result of missing, discoloured, or spoilt teeth [9]. Due to the rise in bacterial isolates resistant to the previous antibiotics in prescription practices, dentists and other dental professionals have recently changed their focus from prescribing narrow-spectrum antibiotics to broad-spectrum aminopenicillins [8,10,11]. While there are many different kinds of dental diseases, we mostly concentrate on periodontal disease, gingivitis, and tooth decay.

Periodontal disease: Bacterial colonisation causes Parkinson's disease (PD), a chronic inflammatory condition that damages the hard and soft tissues supporting teeth [12]. An increase in teeth brushing frequency lowers the concentration of systemic inflammatory marker levels in blood; hence, oral hygiene is a potential way to change the stroke risk. Poor oral hygiene is a contributing factor to both Parkinson's disease and caries [13]. In the early stages of the disease, periodontal disorders are thought to be asymptomatic, ranging from mildly inflamed gums and bleeding upon probing. However, as the disease progresses, it can become more severe, leading to pocket formation, bone loss, and looseness. At this point, it may be difficult to save, so time is crucial and informative [14,15]. As a result, there are four phases to the disease's severity and management complexity:

Stage I: Initial Periodontitis.

Stage II: Moderate Periodontitis.

Stage III: Severe periodontitis that may result in more tooth loss.

Stage IV: Severe periodontitis that may result in dental loss

Gingivitis: A bacterial infection is the most prevalent cause of gingivitis, an inflammatory disease of the gums or gingival tissue. It is gingival inflammation without loss of attachment, meaning that the connective tissue's attachment to the tooth is still intact. Only the connective tissue and gingival epithelium's soft tissue are affected [16]. The symptoms of gingivitis include redness and puffiness in the afflicted area as well as bleeding when probed. It is linked to an inflammatory response to pro-inflammatory cytokines, which are known to balance humoral and cell-mediated immune responses [17]. Plaque-induced gingivitis, infectious gingivitis, nutritional gingivitis, hormonal gingivitis, and drug-induced gingivitis are the five forms of gingivitis.

Tooth decay: Dental caries, also referred to as cavities or tooth decay, is a widespread oral health problem that affects people of all ages worldwide. Due to its prevalence and possible effects on general health and quality of life, dental disease continues to be a major public health concern despite breakthroughs in dental care [18]. Microbial activity, host vulnerability, dietary habits, oral hygiene practices, and socioeconomic factors are only a few of the many variables that interact intricately during the illness process. All ages are affected by dental caries; however, children, teenagers, and older adults are more likely to have it. Untreated caries can have negative effects on general health and quality of life in addition to dental health [19].

2. HISTORY OF DENTAL DISEASES

Pre-agricultural societies had low rates of dental decay, but the emergence of farming society approximately 10,000 years ago was associated with a rise in cavities [20]. An infected tooth from Italy partially cleaned with flint tools, between 13,820 and 14,160 years old, represents the oldest known dentistry[21], although a 2017 study suggests that 130,000 years ago the Neanderthals already used rudimentary dentistry tools[22,23]. Dental caries is attributed to a "tooth worm" according to an ancient Sumerian literature [24]. Ancient Egypt, China, Japan, and India have all shown evidence of this idea. The Homeric Hymns also contain references to the worm fable [25], and the surgeon Guy de Chauliac continued to propagate the idea that worms cause tooth decay as late as the 14th century AD [26].

Hippocrates and Aristotle, two ancient Greek philosophers, wrote on dentistry, including how teeth erupt, how to cure gum disease and decay, how to retrieve teeth with forceps, and how to stabilise loose teeth and cracked jaws using wires [27]. As early as 700 BC, the Etruscans in northern Italy used dentures, bridges, and dental appliances made of human or animal teeth joined by gold bands [28,29,30]. By the fifth century BC, the Romans had probably adopted this method. [29,31] In the sixth and fourth centuries BC, the Phoenicians made dentures using gold wire and two ivory teeth [32]. Hesy-Ra was the first "dentist" (greatest of the teeth) in ancient Egypt. The Egyptians used gold wire to bind substitute teeth together. Cornelius Celsus, a Roman physician, wrote a great deal on oral disorders and dental remedies such emollients and astringents that include narcotics.[33] Dental amalgams first emerged in Germany in 1528 and were first recorded in a Tang period medical literature written by the Chinese physician Su Kung in 659.

[34,35]. Focal infection theory, which postulated that teeth with infected necrotic pulps and endodontically treated teeth might leak bacteria or their toxins into the body, causing arthritis and diseases of the kidney, heart, nervous system, gastrointestinal tract, endocrine system, and other systems, led to a terrifying period of tooth extraction for both the treatment of systemic diseases and as a preventative measure against future illness, in the early 1900s. Fortunately, further epidemiological and microbiological research refuted the notion that tooth extraction may improve the health of a person with a systemic illness. The tide of extraction was stemmed [36].

3. PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF PERIODONTAL DISEASE

Key bacteria in the dental biofilm are responsible for the onset and development of periodontitis. These bacteria trigger an inflammatory immune response that damages tissue in those who are vulnerable. In fact, it is well recognised that the host's immune-inflammatory reactions and the pathogenic subgingival biofilm interact intricately to cause periodontal disease. More than 700 different types of bacteria have been found in the subgingival microbiota [37]. Only a few bacteria, including the major periopathogens *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Tannerella forsythia*, *Treponema denticola*, and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, are thought to be closely linked to the development of periodontitis [38]. The sulcular and junctional epithelium (JE) is the initial physical barrier that separates the microorganisms of the dental biofilm from the underlying mucosal connective tissue (CT). The development of periodontitis depends on both the presence of host risk factors and the transition to a dysbiotic biofilm. For example, an abnormal immunological response, including poor

chemotaxis or excessive generation of reactive oxygen species by polymorphonuclear leukocytes (PMN), The periodontium experiences a series of tissue-damaging events when the dysbiotic biofilm is present [39]. Additionally, the body reacts to the biofilm's apical advancement by causing the JE to migrate apically, creating periodontal pockets. Gram-negative anaerobes dominate the subgingival microbiome, which becomes more complex and diverse as periodontal pocket depth increases. A number of powerful virulence factors, such as fimbriae and lectin-type adhesins, a polysaccharide capsule, LPS, hemagglutinins, potent proteinases, toxic metabolic products, outer membrane vesicles, and numerous enzymes, are also produced by important periodontal pathogens. These factors cause and sustain a strong immune response that results in the release of inflammatory mediators from the pocket epithelium [40]. In addition to receptor activator of nuclear factor-kappa B ligand (RANKL) stimulation, the host's increased expression of MMPs and prostaglandin E2 contributes to deepening the pocket and promoting alveolar bone resorption [41,42]. RANKL and its antagonist osteoprotegerin (OPG) are responsible for bone remodelling under normal physiological conditions [43]. Periodontitis disrupts the RANKL/OPG system because RANKL levels are significantly elevated, overwhelming OPG's decoy function and tipping the scales in favour of greater osteolytic activity [44]. It's interesting to note that RANKL can cause EMT by enhancing the nuclear translocation of EMT-associated transcription factors including Snail and Twist [45] and activating the NF- κ B signalling pathway [45,46]. Neutrophils are found in relatively small numbers in the healthy periodontium, but once the bacterial infection triggers the host's pro-inflammatory response, neutrophils are recruited in relatively large numbers and release oxygen radicals and enzymes that work to lower the bacterial load. Periodontal

disease is said to cause an increased neutrophilic response, and the molecules that are meant to eradicate bacteria can cause local tissue damage, which exacerbates the immune response and leads to a persistent inflammatory lesion that does not go away [47].

Inflammatory cell recruitment is a hallmark of the host's early and initial reaction to the dysbiotic subgingival biofilm within the periodontal pocket [48]. The inflammatory cytokine milieu, which is richer in cytokines including TNF- α , IL-1, IL-4, IL-10, interferon- γ , and TGF- β , is also influenced by the expanding immune cell populations at later stages of the disease [49]. Furthermore, RANKL, which promotes bone absorption and disintegration, is produced by CD4+T-cells [50]. As a result, the loss of epithelial integrity creates a pathway for periodontal bacteria to enter the underlying CT, where important fibroblast populations contribute to the defence system by releasing more inflammatory cytokines. Furthermore, in order to prevent periodontal bacteria from invading deeper tissues, they create a fibrous extracellular matrix (ECM) that walls off the inflammatory region [51,52] Under disease conditions, gingival fibroblasts can also secrete more proteolytic enzymes and pro-inflammatory proteins, including as prostaglandin E2 and MMP-2 [53], which aid in the resorption of bone and the destruction of soft tissue. Therefore, there are factors in this inflammatory environment that could lead to the local drive of EMT.

3.1.PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF GINGIVITIS

Periodontitis has been identified as the advanced stage of gingivitis, which has been classified pathophysiological into initial, early, and established phases.

1. Initial lesion: Acute exudative inflammation, increased gingival fluid flow, and neutrophil

migration from the subgingival plexus blood artery in the gingival connective tissue to the gingival sulcus are the hallmarks of this stage. Fibrin builds up in the vicinity of vessels due to a change in the matrix of the connective tissue. Four days after the start of plaque buildup, the first lesion appears. Collagenase and other enzymes released by neutrophils cause collagen to break down. At this stage, the inflammatory infiltrate occupies between 5% and 10% of the connective tissue [54].

2. Early lesion: Delayed hypersensitivity is consistent with the early lesion. It typically manifests one week following the start of plaque accumulation. The clinical symptoms of gingivitis, including as gingival bleeding and redness, begin to manifest at this point. Macrophages and lymphocytes make up 75% of the inflammatory cells in this lesion. There are also a few plasma cells visible. In addition to the inflammatory infiltration that takes up 5% to 15% of the gingival margin's connective tissue, the afflicted area experiences a 60% to 70% reduction in collagen. Additionally, the gingival fluid flow and the number of leukocytes moving to the area continue to rise, and the local fibroblasts experience a number of pathological alterations. The junctional epithelium also has an increase in neutrophils and mononuclear cells. It is unknown how long the early lesion will last; it might last longer than anticipated [54].

3. Established lesion: In this stage, there is a surge in T and B lymphocytes, plasma cells, macrophages, and collagenolytic activity. However, B lymphocytes and plasma cells are the most common cells. At this point, a little gingival pocket with a pocket epithelium is formed. There is a lot of organisations in the lesion. It has been proposed that a decrease in T cells and an increase in B cells and plasma cells is correlated with the severity of gingivitis. There are two possible

outcomes for an established lesion: either it stays stable for months or years, or it develops into a more severe lesion that seems to be connected to a shift in the microbial ecology or gingival infection. After successful periodontal therapy, which raises the quantity of bacteria linked to periodontal health and coincides with a decrease in plasma cells and lymphocytes, this stage might be reversed [54].

4. Advanced lesion: This phase is a prelude to periodontitis. Irreversible attachment loss is its defining feature. The supporting tissues of the teeth and adjacent structures, such as the gingiva, periodontal ligament, and alveolar bone, are impacted by the inflammatory changes and bacterial infection, which can cause tooth loss [55,56].

3.2. PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF TOOTH DECAY

Enamel: The direction of the enamel rods, the various triangular patterns between pit and fissure, and the development of smooth-surface caries all contribute to the demineralisation of enamel by caries [57]. The enamel develops a number of unique zones as it loses minerals, including the translucent zone, dark zones, body of the lesion, and surface zone [58]. A 1/2% loss of minerals corresponds with the translucent zone [59]. Enamel is slightly remineralised in the dark zone. The lesion's body has the most demineralisation and damage. Until the tooth structure is lost and a cavitation occurs, the surface zone stays largely mineralised [60].

Dentine: The advancing front, the zone of bacterial penetration, and the zone of destruction

are the three distinct regions impacted by caries in dentine, ranging from the deepest layer to the enamel [57]. The advancing front is a region of acid-demineralized dentine devoid of microorganisms. The areas where bacteria invade and eventually break down dentin are known as the zones of bacterial penetration and destruction. Proteolytic enzymes have degraded the organic matrix, resulting in a more diverse bacterial population in the destruction zone [59].

Cementum: When gingival collapse results from periodontal disease or trauma, the incidence of cemental caries rises in older persons. It is a long-term illness that starts as a big, shallow lesion and gradually spreads to the cementum and dentin of the root, resulting in a persistent pulp infection [61].

Figure 1. Flowchart of pathogenesis of dental caries

Some common drugs that are used in the dental diseases

Drug Name	Structure	Mechanism of action	Reference
Metronidazole		Metronidazole is reduced in anaerobes to reactive radicals that disrupt microbial DNA, inhibiting nucleic acid synthesis and causing cell death	(62)
Amoxicillin		Amoxicillin binds penicillin-binding proteins, inhibits bacterial cell wall peptidoglycan Cross-linking, weakening wall, leading to osmotic lysis and death of bacteria.	(63)
Cefixime		Cefixime, a third-generation cephalosporin, binds to penicillin-binding proteins (PBPs) and inhibits bacterial cell wall peptidoglycan synthesis, leading to a weakened cell wall, osmotic lysis, and bacterial death.	(62)
Doxycycline		Doxycycline (a tetracycline antibiotic) binds to the 30S ribosomal subunit of bacteria and blocks attachment of aminoacyl-tRNA to the mRNA-ribosome complex, thereby inhibiting protein synthesis and stopping bacterial growth (bacteriostatic).	(63)

Drugs that are used in Periodontal disease

Drug Name	Structure	Mechanism of action	Reference
Minocycline		Minocycline (a tetracycline antibiotic) binds to the 30S ribosomal subunit of bacteria and prevents attachment of aminoacyl-tRNA to the mRNA-ribosome complex, thereby inhibiting protein synthesis and acting as a bacteriostatic agent.	(62)

Ciprofloxacin		Ciprofloxacin inhibits bacterial DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV, preventing DNA replication, transcription, and repair, leading to bactericidal action.	(63)
Alendronate		Alendronate is a bisphosphonate that binds to hydroxyapatite in bone and is taken up by osteoclasts during bone resorption. It inhibits farnesyl pyrophosphate synthase (FPPS) in the mevalonate pathway, leading to osteoclast dysfunction and apoptosis, thereby reducing bone resorption and increasing bone mineral density.	(63)
Acetaminophen		Acetaminophen produces analgesic and antipyretic effects primarily by inhibiting cyclo-oxygenase (COX) activity in the central nervous system, leading to reduced prostaglandin synthesis. It also acts on the hypothalamic heat-regulating centre, lowering fever. It has minimal peripheral anti-inflammatory action.	(63)
Diazepam (sedative)		Diazepam is a benzodiazepine that enhances the inhibitory action of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) by binding to the GABA _A receptor. It increases the frequency of chloride channel opening, leading to neuronal hyperpolarization and CNS depression.	(63)

Drugs that are used in gingivitis disease

Drug Name	Structure	Mechanism of action	Reference
Chlorhexidine (Antiseptic)		Chlorhexidine is a cationic bisbiguanide antiseptic that binds to bacterial cell membranes, increasing membrane permeability. At low concentrations, it is bacteriostatic by disrupting membrane integrity; at high concentrations, it causes precipitation of cellular	(63)

		proteins, leading to bactericidal action.	
Gluconate		Gluconate" itself has no single MOA — it's just a salt/formulation. The mechanism depends on the active substance paired with gluconate	(63)
Benzydamine HCl		Benzydamine HCl is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) with local analgesic and anti-inflammatory action. It inhibits pro-inflammatory cytokine synthesis (e.g., TNF- α , IL-1 β) and stabilizes cell membranes, reducing vascular permeability, edema, and pain. It also shows local anaesthetic and antimicrobial effects.	(63)
Cetylpyridinium chloride		Cetylpyridinium chloride is a cationic quaternary ammonium antiseptic that binds to negatively charged microbial cell membranes, causing disruption of membrane integrity. This leads to leakage of intracellular contents, protein denaturation, and cell death, resulting in bactericidal action, especially against Gram-positive bacteria.	(63)
Hyaluronic acid		Hyaluronic acid is a natural glycosaminoglycan that binds and retains water, forming a viscoelastic, lubricating, and protective matrix. It maintains tissue hydration, enhances wound healing, and reduces inflammation by protecting cells and facilitating tissue repair.	(64)

Drug that are used in the tooth decay

Drug Name	Structure	Mechanism of action	Reference
Silver diamine fluoride		Silver diamine fluoride exerts its effect by silver ions denaturing bacterial proteins and damaging cell walls, producing a strong antimicrobial action, while fluoride ions promote remineralization of	(64)

		enamel and inhibit demineralization. It also arrests dental caries by inhibiting collagen degradation in dentin.	
Sodium fluoride	$\text{Na}^+ \cdots \text{F}^-$	Sodium fluoride enhances remineralization of tooth enamel by promoting formation of fluorapatite, which is more resistant to acid dissolution. It also inhibits bacterial glycolytic enzymes, reducing acid production by oral bacteria, thereby preventing dental caries.	(64)
Casein phosphopeptide		Casein phosphopeptide (CPP) bind calcium and phosphate ions, forming stable amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP) complexes. These complexes deliver bioavailable calcium and phosphate to enamel, enhancing remineralization and preventing demineralization of teeth. CPP-ACP also buffers plaque pH, reducing acid-mediated enamel damage.	(65)
Xylitol		Xylitol is a non-fermentable sugar alcohol that inhibits growth of <i>Streptococcus mutans</i> by interfering with bacterial glycolysis, reducing acid production. It also promotes remineralization of enamel by increasing salivary calcium and phosphate levels, helping prevent dental caries.	(66)

CONCLUSION

Dental diseases, particularly dental caries, gingivitis, and periodontitis, continue to pose significant public health challenges globally due to their high prevalence and impact on overall well-being. Dental caries, as a chronic infectious disease, results from the complex interplay of microbial activity, host susceptibility, dietary habits, and time. If left untreated, it can lead to pain, tooth loss, and functional impairments affecting nutrition, communication, and quality of life.

The progression of gingivitis to periodontitis highlights the critical role of early detection and

intervention. The underlying pathophysiology involves a dysbiotic microbial environment and an exaggerated host immune-inflammatory response, ultimately leading to destruction of supporting tooth structures. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for developing effective preventive and therapeutic strategies.

Modern dentistry emphasizes prevention through oral hygiene practices, dietary control, and the use of remineralizing agents such as fluoride. Pharmacological management, including antibiotics, antiseptics, and anti-inflammatory drugs, plays a supportive role in controlling infection and inflammation. However, the

emergence of antibiotic resistance necessitates cautious and rational use of these medications.

In conclusion, maintaining good oral health requires a comprehensive approach that integrates prevention, early diagnosis, and appropriate treatment. Public health awareness, regular dental check-ups, and advancements in preventive and therapeutic modalities are essential to reduce the global burden of dental diseases and enhance overall health outcomes.

REFERENCES

1. Thean H, Wong ML and Koh H. The dental awareness of nursing home staff in Singapore—a pilot study. *Gerodontology*. 2007; 24: 58-63.
2. Petersen PE, Bourgeois D, Ogwa H, Estupinan-Day S, and Ndiaye C. The global burden of disease and risks to oral health. *Bull world health organ*. 2005; 83: 661-669.
3. Swetha P. Immunology of Dental Caries: A Review. *Int J Curr Adv Res*. 2018;7(6):13117–23.
4. Kumari MR, Samson R et al. A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme on Knowledge regarding Dental Caries among School Students in Rural Areas of Anichakuppam, Puducherry. *Asian Journal of Nursing Education and Research*. 2019;9(4): 545-548. doi: 10.5958/2349-2996.2019.00117.4
5. Suganya M, Yadavi Soondron MR. Oral and Dietary Habits, and Immunological and Clinical Impacts on the Incidence of Dental Caries—A Review. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*. 2014;7(11):1348-53.
6. Janakiram C, Antony B, Joseph J, Ramanarayanan V. Prevalence of Dental Caries in India among the WHO Index Age Groups: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Clinical & Diagnostic Research*. 2018;12(8). doi:10.7860/JCDR/2018/32669.11956
7. Yadav K, Prakash S, Yadav NP, Sah RS (2015) Multi-Drug resistance of Bacterial isolates among Dental Caries Patients. *Janaki Medical College Journal of Medical Sci* 3: 37-44.
8. De Marchi RJ, Hugo FN, Padilha DM, Hilgert JB, Machado DB, et al. (2011) Edentulism, use of dentures and consumption of fruit and vegetables in south Brazilian community-dwelling elderly. *J Oral Rehabil* 38: 533-540.
9. Yadav K, Prakash S (2017) Dental Caries: A Review. *Asian J of Biomed and Pharmaceutical Sci* 6: 1-7.
10. Yadav K, Prakash S (2015) Antibigram profiles against polymicrobial pathogens among dental caries patients at Janaki Medical College teaching hospital, Nepal. *Int J Applied Dental Sci* 1: 156-162.
11. Al-Haroni M, Skaug N (2007) Incidence of antibiotic prescribing in dental practice in Norway, its contribution to national consumption. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 59: 1161-1166.
12. Pihlstrom BL, Michalowicz BS, Johnson NW. Periodontal diseases. *Lancet*. 2005;366(9499):1809-1820.
13. de Oliveira C, Watt R, Hamer M. Toothbrushing, inflammation, and risk of cardiovascular disease: results from Scottish health survey. *BMJ* 2010;340:c2451.
14. Herrera D, Meyle J, Renvert S, Jin L (2018) White Paper on Prevention and Management of Periodontal Diseases for Oral Health and General Health. *FDI World Dent* 20: 1-20.
15. Kinane DF, Stathopoulou PG, Papapanou PN (2017) Periodontal diseases. *Nat Rev Dis Prim* 3: 17038
16. Marchesan JT, Girnary MS, Moss K, Monaghan ET, Egnatz GJ, Jiao Y, Zhang S,

- Beck J, Swanson KV. Role of inflammasomes in the pathogenesis of periodontal disease and therapeutics. *Periodontol.* 2000. 2020 Feb;82(1):93-114. [PMC free article: PMC6927484] [PubMed: 31850638]
17. Shimada Y, Tabeta K, Sugita N, Yoshie H. Profiling biomarkers in gingival crevicular fluid using multiplex bead immunoassay. *Arch. Oral Biol.* 2013 Jun;58(6):724-30. [PubMed: 23395670].
 18. Tun KM, Imwong M, Lwin KM, Win AA, Hlaing TM, et al. (2015) Spread of artemisinin-resistant *Plasmodium falciparum* in Myanmar: a cross-sectional survey of the K13 molecular marker. *THE LANCET Infectious Diseases* 15: 415-421.
 19. Baragana B, Hallyburton I, Lee MC, Norcross NR, Grimaldi R, et al. (2015) A novel multiple-stage antimalarial agent that inhibits protein synthesis. *Nature* 522: 315-320.
 20. Barras, Colin (29 February 2016). "How our ancestors drilled rotten teeth". BBC. Archived from the original on 19 May 2017. Retrieved 1 March 2016.
 21. "Oldest Dentistry Found in 14,000-Year-Old Tooth". DNews. Discovery Channel. 16 July 2015. Archived from the original on 18 July 2015. Retrieved 21 July 2015.
 22. Sherif, Ekramy (5 April 2006). "Platinum Dental". Retrieved 20 December 2025.
 23. "Analysis of Neanderthal teeth marks uncovers evidence of prehistoric dentistry". The University of Kansas. 28 June 2017. Retrieved 1 July 2017.
 24. "History of Dentistry: Ancient Origins". American Dental Association. Archived from the original on 5 July 2007. Retrieved 9 January 2007.
 25. TOWNEND, B. R. (1944). "The Story of the Tooth-Worm". *Bulletin of the History of Medicine.* 15 (1): 37–58. ISSN 0007-5140. JSTOR 44442797.
 26. Suddick Richard P., Harris Norman O. (1990). "Historical Perspectives of Oral Biology: A Series" (PDF). *Critical Reviews in Oral Biology and Medicine.* 1 (2): 135–51. doi:10.1177/10454411900010020301. PMID 2129621. Archived from the original (PDF) on 18 December 2007.
 27. "History Of Dentistry". *Complete Dental Guide.* Archived from the original on 14 July 2016. Retrieved 29 June 2016.
 28. "History of Dentistry Research Page, Newsletter". Rcpsg.ac.uk. Archived from the original on 28 April 2015. Retrieved 9 June 2014.
 29. Donaldson, J. A. (1980). "The use of gold in dentistry" (PDF). *Gold Bulletin.* 13 (3): 117–124. doi:10.1007/BF03216551. PMID 11614516. S2CID 137571298.
 30. Becker, Marshall J. (1999). Ancient "dental implants": a recently proposed example from France evaluated with other spurious examples (PDF). *International Journal of Oral & Maxillofacial Implants* 14.1.
 31. Malik, Ursman. "History of Dentures from Beginning to Early 19th Century". Exhibits. Retrieved 3 May 2023
 32. Renfrew, Colin; Bahn, Paul (2012). *Archaeology: Theories, Methods, and Practice* (6th ed.). Thames & Hudson. p. 449. ISBN 978-0-500-28976-1.
 33. "Dental Treatment in the Ancient Times". *DentalTreatment.org.uk.* Archived from the original on 1 December 2009. Retrieved 18 April 2010.
 34. Bjørklund G (1989). "The history of dental amalgam (in Norwegian)". *Tidsskr Nor Laegeforen.* 109 (34–36): 3582–85. PMID 2694433.
 35. Czarnetzki, A.; Ehrhardt S. (1990). "Re-dating the Chinese amalgam-filling of teeth in

- Europe". *International Journal of Anthropology*. 5 (4): 325–32
36. Indramohan J, Karthika B, Mohiddin G. Myth of endodontics in oral focal infection *Indian J Multidiscip Dent*. 2012; 2:380–2.
37. Kumar PS, Griffen AL, Moeschberger ML, Leys EJ. Identification of candidate periodontal pathogens and beneficial species by quantitative 16S clonal ana lysis. *J Clin Microbiol* 2005; 43:3944–55.
38. Lovegrove JM. Dental plaque revisited: bacteria associated with periodontal disease. *J N Z Soc Periodo* 2004:7–21.
39. Scott DA, Krauss J. Neutrophils in periodontal inflammation. *Front Oral Biol* 2012; 15:56–83.
40. Tribble GD, Lamont RJ. Bacterial invasion of epithelial cells and spreading in periodontal tissue. *Periodontol* 2000 2010; 52:68–83.
41. Kornman KS, Page RC, Tonetti MS. The host response to the microbial challenge in periodontitis: assembling the players. *Periodontol* 2000 1997; 14:33–53.
42. Hannas AR, Pereira JC, Granjeiro JM, Tjäderhane L. The role of matrix metalloproteinases in the oral environment. *Acta Odontol Scand* 2007; 65:1–13.
43. Boyce BF, Xing L. The RANKL/RANK/OPG pathway. *Curr Osteoporos Rep* 2007; 5:98–104.
44. Belibasakis GN, Bostanci N. The RANKL-OPG system in clinical periodontology. *J Clin Periodo* 2012; 39:239–48.
45. Tsubaki M, Komai M, Fujimoto S, Itoh T, Imano M, Sakamoto K, et al. Activation of NF- κ B by the RANKL/RANK system up-regulates snail and twist expressions and induces epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition in mammary tumor cell lines. *J Exp Clin Cancer Res* 2013; 32:62.
46. Palafox M, Ferrer I, Pellegrini P, Vila S, Hernandez-Ortega S, Urruticoechea A, et al. RANK induces epithelial-mesenchymal transition and stemness in human mammary epithelial cells and promotes tumorigenesis and metastasis. *Cancer Res* 2012; 72:2879–88.
47. Chapple ILC, Gilbert AD, Wilson NHF. *Understanding Periodontal Diseases: Assessment and Diagnostic Procedures in Practice*. London, England: Quintessence Publishing Co; 2002.
48. Benakanakere M, Kinane DF. Innate cellular responses to the periodontal bio f ilm. *Front Oral Biol* 2011; 15:41–55.
49. Graves D. Cytokines that promote periodontal tissue destruction. *J Periodo* 2008; 79:1585–91.
50. Vernal R, Dutzan N, Hernández M, Chandía S, Puente J, León R, et al. High ex pression levels of receptor activator of nuclear factor-kappa B ligand associated with human chronic periodontitis are mainly secreted by CD4+ T lymphocytes. *J Periodo* 2006; 77:1772–80.
51. Ahn SH, Chun S, Park C, Lee J, Lee JH, Lee SW, Lee TH. Transcriptome profiling analysis of senescent gingival fibroblasts in response to *Fusobacterium nucleatum* infection. *PLoS One* 2017; 12: e0188755.
52. Palm E, Khalaf H, Bengtsson T. *Porphyromonas gingivalis* downregulates the immune response of fibroblasts. *BMC Microbiol* 2013; 13:155.
53. Page RC, Kornman KS. The pathogenesis of human periodontitis: an introduction. *Periodontol* 2000 1997; 14:9–11.
54. Page RC. Gingivitis. *J Clin Periodontol*. 1986 May; 13(5):345-59. [PubMed]
55. Bosshardt DD, Selvig KA. Dental cementum: the dynamic tissue covering of the root. *Periodontol* 2000. 1997 Feb; 13:41-75. [PubMed]

56. Syndergaard B, Al-Sabbagh M, Kryscio RJ, Xi J, Ding X, Ebersole JL, Miller CS. Salivary biomarkers associated with gingivitis and response to therapy. *J Periodontol.* 2014 Aug;85(8): e295-303. [PMC free article] [PubMed]
57. Kidd EA and Fejerskov O. What constitutes dental caries? Histopathology of carious enamel and dentin related to the action of cariogenic biofilms. *J Dent Res.* 2004; 83: 35–38.
58. Darling AI. Resistance of the enamel to dental caries. *J Dent Res.* 1963; 42(1) 2: 488–496.
59. Robinson C, Shore RC, Brookes SJ, Strafford S, Wood SR and Kirkham J. The chemistry of enamel caries. *Crit Rev Oral Biol Med.* 2000; 11: 481–495.
60. Nanci. *Ten Cate's Oral Histology.* 7th edition. Elsevier, 2013; pp 115-121
61. Balogh B and Fehrenbach. *Illustrated Embryology, Histology, and Anatomy.* 4th edition. Elsevier, 2011; pp 352.
62. Brunton LL, Hilal-Dandan R, Knollmann BC. *Goodman & Gilman's The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics.* 13th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill; 2018.
63. Katzung BG, Vanderah TW. *Basic & Clinical Pharmacology.* 15th ed. McGraw-Hill; 2021.
64. *Goodman & Gilman's The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics.* 13th ed.
65. Ten Cate JM. Enamel Remineralization and the Role of Casein Phosphopeptide-Amorphous Calcium Phosphate. *Journal of Dentistry,* 1998;26:1–10.
66. Marsh PD. Dental plaque as a biofilm and a microbial community – implications for health and disease. *BMC Oral Health.* 2006;6(Suppl 1): S14.

HOW TO CITE: Nidhika Rana, Nikhil Koundal, Sneha, Avinash, Muskan, Nitika, Oral Health Disorders: An Integrative Review of Dental Caries, Gingivitis, and Periodontitis, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 5609-5622. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20328050>

